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Tourism Trends of Millennial Tourists

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ABSTRACT

Millennials are considered to cover individuals born between 1980-1996. This generation in literature is also described as the Internet Belt, Millennials, Echo Boomers, Generation Next, Nexters. The core values of this generation are innovation, independence, creativity, ambition and development. More egocentric than other generations, millennials are fond of brands, friends, entertainment and digital culture. Y-generation, a self-confident, educated generation, has a different perspective on business life, consumption style and social relations. In the next 10 years, millennials will make up 75% of the global workforce. It is estimated that vacation and travel will be an indispensable item for the Y generation. Therefore, it will reveal a number of opportunities for the travel and hospitality industry. There will also be differentiations in tourism trends for this generation, which prefers travel programs to have different experiences in travel and sightseeing preferences. Finally, examples of research on tourism trends among millennials (wellness tourism, camping, solo traveller, spiritual tourism and yoga vacations) were examined. This paper will contribute to literature in this subject and it can be said that this study has a quality that will lead to academic research and that it is a research that tourism sector can benefit from it.

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1. Introduction

Generation theory was born from the idea that individuals born in the same period and affected by the same economic, technological and political changes share similar values, behaviors and lifestyles (Chen, 2010, p. 132). Understanding generations is one of the issues that need to be addressed in many sectors. Similarly, understanding generations in the tourism sector contributes to the sector's making the necessary preparations in accordance with consumer characteristics, needs and expectations. More and more diversity between generations today plays an increasingly significant role in understanding tourist behavior.

The concept of “*generation*” is used both to categorize age groups defined as groups of people born at a similar time, and also to analyze people in various subjects, behaviors and characteristics. Today, the majority of individuals of the millennials are married, have double earnings, and have become a standard that guarantees good conditions for their children's personal development. For this generation, respect for ethics, multiculturalism, awareness of social problems, use of information and communication technology are of great importance. Millennials, who are extremely mobile, are individuals who travel willingly, move from one place to another and are not ready to make the decision to migrate quickly because of economic reasons. Millennials travel more than past generations, visit more places and discover more locations in their destinations. Although they spend more on their travels, they are more eager for interesting experiences and information (Vukić et al., 2015). They are especially environmentally friendly tourists who do not want to be more independent, who prefer travel for special interests rather than mass tourism.

In the tourism sector, in order to divide the market into segments and reach potential customers, the method of separating tourists according to age groups is preferred. In particular, an age-based segmentation is used to reach consumers by taking into account the similar characteristics, expectations and desires. In this context, the characteristics of millennials, tourist behavior, travel preferences and travel tendencies are emphasized in the study. In addition, the actual data of the research results on millennials are included. As a result of the researches, it has been determined that millennials especially those who go on business trips add touristic activities to their travels and love to experience adventure and new experiences. It has been determined that the millennials are interested in tourism types such as wellness, spiritual tourism, yoga tourism, solo tourism, and the demand for camping tourism has increased with the understanding of the importance of distance especially after the COVID-19 epidemic.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Generations

Although the multiple generation theory was first proposed by Mannheim in 1952, it gained its popularity with the work of Inglehart (1977) and Strauss and Howe (1991). Straus and Howe introduced the “generational theory” in 1991 and dealt with different eras with four acres, each alternating between 20-22 years. Within these acres, they grouped the generations with different characteristics (Traditionalists, Baby Boomers, Generation X and Millennials). In this theory, they mentioned that individuals born and raised at certain periods, within the same age group, have similar behavioral characteristics and that their behavioral characteristics differ with each new generation (Arslan & Staub, 2015, p. 5). Strauss and Howe's division of generations into groups according to historical data and Mannheim's holistic and sociological attitude are the two rival theories about generations in the scientific world. Although there is no scientifically definite and unconditionally accepted theory of generations, there are generally accepted groupings that are used to legitimize generations and handle them reliably (Strauss & Howe, 1997, p. 2; Benckendorff et al., 2010).

Assuming that the generation is an identifiable group of people who share similar birth dates and experiences of significant events in their developmental stages, there are four generations in scientific literature (Dolot, 2018). As a result of recent studies, Generation Z and Generation Alpha have been added to the Silent Generation, Baby Boomers, Generation X and Millennials. The characteristics of these generations can be briefly explained as follows (McCrindle, 2014):

- Silent Generation (Traditionalists): It consists of individuals who were born in 1945 and before.
- Baby Boomers: Born in 1945–1964, it is the generation of the baby boom and the economic boom.
- Generation X: It is the group born in 1965-1980 that grew up during the economic crisis of the 1970s.
- Millennials: Born in 1981-1994, it is the group that grew in the age of globalization and universal access to the internet.
- Generation Z: It is defined as the generation that was born after 1995 and uses modern information and communication technologies in every possible situation.
- Generation Alpha: The next generation from Generation Z consists of individuals born after 2010. This generation consists of children aged ten and under. Therefore, they are not considered in most detailed studies.

Millennials as a niche market are affected by the social environment and social media in their demands and consumption trends and their purchasing behavior (Madrigal Moreno et al., 2017, p. 140). While representatives of this generation rely on information they find on the Internet, face-to-face communication still has a significant impact on their choices. In addition to this, they tend to trust their friends and families more from their websites (Monaco, 2018, p. 4). Millennials are aware of what they can expect from a product or service purchased at any price. Therefore, millennials seek high quality in product and service delivery. However, they are willing to pay extra when they believe that the product, service or experience is worth it (Benckendorff et al., 2010, p. 159).

Millennials spend their income quicker than previous generations. The philosophy of their life is indicated in the motto “enjoy the date”. In addition, since it is very important for this generation to balance personal life and business life, millennials travel regularly and loves collective learning. At the same time, millennials constantly share their ideas and love to use their knowledge to be accepted as experts and to influence their peers (Madrigal Moreno et al., 2017, p. 104).

Millennials use personal computers more than mobile devices. However, they combine the use of the internet with more traditional communication tools (telephone or magazines, etc.) to gather information and make purchasing decisions. Their technological capabilities enable them to advertise positive or negative brands that they consider reliable. In addition, when brands try to communicate with millennials, they are able to establish an effective communication. In this sense, they can use digital marketing as a tool to get the ideas of millennials in offering attractive and special offers to millennial consumers, personalizing products and developing new products (Genç, 2019, p. 38). Millennials are heavily involved in consumption and they consume more on online sites and social media (e.g. Facebook). In this context, businesses need to train social network administrators to immediately respond to the demands of millennials and develop useful applications in order to make a continuous content update (Madrigal Moreno et al., 2017, p. 140).

2.2. Millennials' travel preferences

The desire of millennials to consume for experience purposes constitutes a large customer segment in hotels. It provides the opportunity to make easy comparisons with the travelers sharing their holiday experiences. In addition, since millennials have become the source of connection in mobile devices, it makes it easier to make a decision because it allows price comparison and therefore they make easier decisions to complete their shopping. Millennial tourists are now beyond a

niche market. Many destinations around the world allocate significant resources to develop the tourism segment for millennials.

According to a research by the American Center for Hospitality Industry Research, millennials will make up 50% of all travelers in America by 2025. Millennials travel preferences differ from traditional travel preferences. Millennials research on the destinations they will travel to, and exploring local heritage and traditions is the first reason for travel. In addition, 90% of millennial tourists want to have unique experiences that differ from their daily lives. Therefore, private sector and public institutions need to synthesize different age groups, their characteristics, life experiences, issues that are important to them, renew their products and keep up with the changing era in order to win the millennial consumers (Perçin & Mahmutoğulları, 2018, p. 14).

For millennial tourists, friendliness, flexibility and comfort are key words, and today 76% of millennials choose traditional hotels for their travels. Creativity is another subject of interest for the Y generation tourists who want to visit at any time and wish their favorite shops and restaurants to be open in the middle of the night. Environmentally conscious businesses with high social responsibility are attractive for millennials. For the members of this generation who prefer healthy and delicious foods, it is the most natural act for them to directly express their likes and to make critical comments immediately (Perçin & Mahmutoğulları, 2018, p. 14).

Some hotel businesses are making changes in their concepts for the increasing millennial tourists, and especially, they are implementing holiday and travel projects that include fast internet and the latest technological infrastructure. It is among the issues that should be taken into consideration by tourism businesses, where millennial tourists have high environmental awareness, love surprises, wonder about different experiences and visit places where they can establish intimate relationships. In addition, tourism businesses need to keep up with the change, as the majority of those who have recently traveled will be millennial tourists. Within this, the concepts of “personalized experiences”, “digital comfort” and “information required in social media” stand out as the three most important instruments (Avcıkurt, 2018).

According to a study conducted by Ehotelier.com website, the travel preferences of millennials can be listed as follows (Caroll, 2016):

- 21% of millennial tourists make their hotel choices via tablets and 55% via mobile phones. The rate of those who use desktop computers for hotel reservations is 87%. Desktop computers are still the most used tool for hotel reservations.
- According to the researches, it is found that this generation has benefited from early booking opportunities. It was determined that 31% of millennials made their

hotel reservations 1 to 3 months in advance, and 29% made their hotel reservations 1 to 3 weeks before. The rate of those who have their trips when there is more than 3 months left is 11%, and the rate of those who do it when there is less than a week left is 9%.

- While 65% of the respondents have traveled at least once in 12 months, most of them stated that they see these trips as an opportunity for business and leisure.
- 83% of millennials get advice for hotel accommodation from colleagues, family and close friends.
- Millennials also cited TripAdvisor as their most trusted source of online reviews with 81%.

3. Methodology

The aim of this study is to mention the importance of age segments for the tourism sector. Today, the majority of those who participate in tourism activities are Y generation. For this reason, the characteristics of the Y generation, tourist behaviors, travel preferences and travel tendencies are emphasized. In this study, literature review and document review, which is one of the qualitative research methods, was carried out. In the study, an index study was made about the tourism trends of Y generation tourists in recent years. National and international theses and articles that can be accessed within the scope of the research were carried out by scanning. It has been determined that the Y generation is interested in tourism types such as wellness, spiritual tourism, yoga tourism, solo tourism, camp tourism.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Trends in millennial tourism

Millennial tourists, who are the main source of the postmodern tourism paradigm where advanced technology and individualization are experienced, gave their first members in the 1980s. It is an important generation that is currently engaged in tourism behavior and will be a potential tourist for a long time in the future. Millennials, whose expectations and demands differ from previous generations, are extremely sensitive to the environment, are interested in the culture of their destination, and always desire to learn and experience unique experiences, and are indispensable elements of the “new tourism”. According to the concept of “new tourism”, in the 21st century, visitors are individuals who attach importance to ecological and sustainable development and enjoy authentic experiences. This situation reveals the changing tourist profile (Seçilmiş & Köz, 2015). Some of the tourism trends of millennial tourists are explained below.

Generation Y members whose expectations and demands differ from previous generations, who are extremely sensitive to the environment, who are interested in the culture of their destination, and who always desire to learn and experience unique experiences are indispensable elements of the concept of “new tourism”.

4.1.1. Wellness tourism

Wellness tourism, which is a type of tourism that covers both physical and mental health, is especially preferred by those who care about their health, and those who aim to escape from the negative effects of modern life. Wellness is a life philosophy based on being healthier by keeping body, spirit and mental health in balance (Ergüven, 2010, p. 1). Wellness is defined as a combination of health and happiness, and body care is included in the scope of wellness with nature and natural products such as massage, skin care, thalassotherapy, mud and moss baths, bathtub treatments that make the person feel mentally, physically, mentally and relationally well and fit (Değer, 2020, pp. 311-312). Recently, the demand for businesses providing wellness services has been increasing especially for the purpose of physical health and beauty. For this reason, hotel businesses also have SPA and Wellness centers within their structure in order to respond to customer demands.

Thanks to detox, meditation and various therapies provided by experts in wellness businesses, it gives the person the opportunity to regain body health with detox (purification from toxins), which eliminates many problems such as unnatural medicine, processed food, accumulation of polluted air in the body, chronic fatigue, sleep problems. In addition, it provides the opportunity to get rid of the negative effects of the intensity of work life and stress with meditation and various massages. Although all aspects of wellness tourism are at an important point, the place of spiritual wellness has become more important in recent days. Nowadays, tourists tend to seek new life experiences rather than travel exclusively for cultural, social or leisure purposes. With these new experiences, tourism creates a spiritual journey for tourists, and travels arrive at yoga tourism, a gateway to spirituality. In short, the spiritual dimension is part of new forms of tourism. One of these parts is wellness and the second is holistic tourism. Holistic tourism gains power in the modern world with tourists following programs and experiences that they believe will provide balance in their lives. The desire of tourists to have a holistic harmony between body, soul and mind and to experience an inner life by moving away from the routine life order has created a new segment for spiritual experiences. Some researchers define this new tourism as a high-level prosperity product (Rocha et al., 2016).

4.1.2. Camping

Camping is a form of recreation performed by making use of accommodation vehicles such as tents, huts, caravans for different purposes such as having recreational or sports activities in nature, staying for a short time, resting. Campings / camping areas, which are the places where this activity is held, are areas that are established in highways routes and their immediate surroundings, at city entrances, in places with natural beauty such as sea, lakes and mountains, and where campers generally meet their overnight, eating and drinking, entertainment, recreation and sports needs with their own means (Aksöz et al., 2020, p. 448). Camp tourism stands out as a lively accommodation vehicle, especially in terms of symbolizing “freedom”.

The number of caravaners described with the analogy of “the snail carrying its house on its back” (Lashley, 2015, p. 115) is increasing day by day. Especially during the pandemic period, camping and caravan tourism has become a more demanded tourism activity in order to provide a comfortable social distance and to avoid the risk of contamination. In this respect, camping and caravan tourism is among the preferences of those who are in search of “isolated vacation” (Şengel et al., 2020, p. 1435).

Camp tourism offers an opportunity to increase the welfare of the local community as well as protecting the nature. On the other hand, it includes positive features such as ensuring the development of regions that are less developed in terms of tourism, bringing together tourists and local communities at a common point and providing interaction between them. Besides, in addition to protecting the environment, it provides the opportunity to integrate the individuals with the natural life, to rest in the countryside, to experience the local cuisine, to see the diversity of animals and plants closely (Aksöz et al., 2020, p. 448). Among the factors that are effective in participating in camping tourism are being economic, socialization, and desire to be in the natural environment, environmental and spiritual factors. The characteristics of camping tourism that are effective in individuals' preference for camping tourism are as follows (Sarı, 2007, p. 318):

- being places with natural beauties such as rivers and forests;
- to give nature lovers the opportunity to live in nature;
- to raise environmental awareness;
- economic contribution to the region;
- having the freedom to take a break and pause at will;
- it allows the balance of nature without concreting;
- providing accommodation diversity;
- attractive for individuals of all ages;

- bringing people with similar hobbies together;
- it covers four seasons.

4.1.3. Solo travel

The history of solo travel goes back to the travels of backpackers. In the 1990s, the terminology “backpacker tourist” began to be widely used for the concepts of an explorer or researcher. Although the term “backpackers” are frequently used in tourism literature, today, solo travel movement is becoming more common, defining individuals who want to travel alone and experience a sense of discovery (Pereira & Silva, 2018, p. 135). This type of tourist is young and a budget tourists who spend a long time on vacation (Loker-Murphy & Pearce, 1995). Most backpackers travel alone or in small groups, seeking suitable travel conditions, and are very flexible in their accommodation and tourism preferences (Scheyvens, 2002). This tourist group seeks experiences that are a journey of discovery and wants to explore unusual places. Nowadays, demographic changes, people staying single for a long time, increasingly active elderly population and changes in lifestyles affect the travel decisions and demands of tourists (Valaja, 2018, p. 5). From this point the reasons people prefer solo alone are as follows:

- being responsible for person's own travel program;
- loneliness (solitude);
- freedom and independence;
- to meet new people;
- being on the to-do list;
- self-reflection and energy gathering;
- a sense of feeling strong.

Although solo tourists are of all ages, middle-aged single women and men who live in large families and want to travel alone are predominant. Especially in studies for women traveling alone (Yang et al., 2018; Kaba & Emekli, 2018; Valaja, 2018) it has been shown that solo travel is due to changes in social structure and lifestyle and is among the fastest growing tourism market segments. Many solo female tourists seek exotic places and cultural experiences. Others are interested in quiet adventures. Young solo tourists (18-35 years) traveling alone enjoy meeting new people during their vacations. There is a high proportion of male travelers traveling alone to meet new people on their travels. Women traveling alone often prefer excursions such as active and exotic holidays and African safaris. Men, on the other hand, participate in solo trips with demands such as cycling and sailing.

Solo travel statistics (2019) reveal that nowadays the solo travel market constitutes 11% of the total market, and 84% of these are female tourists. Solo female bookings increased by 45% between 2015 and 2017, and 72% of women in the US prefer to travel alone (Solo Traveler, 2019). Similarly, according to the 2018 China Travel Consumer Report, young women born in the 90s and 2000s also prefer to travel independently. According to the study of Yang et al. (2018), many women found that as a result of freedom, independence and economic improvements, they started traveling alone independently. Solo travel is not only considered an escape for women, but also an experience that offers certain opportunities to emancipate with a travel that suits them socially (Karagöz et al., 2021, p. 1).

The most important criterion in destination selection for solo tourists is security. While married solo tourists generally prefer domestic travel, solo tourists are more likely to choose international destinations. After cities and towns, beaches and mountainous areas are the places preferred by solo tourists. According to European tour operators, solo tourists are looking for more adventure. Popular solo tourism destinations in developing countries are Costa Rica, India, Laos, Nepal, Sri Lanka, Vietnam (CBI Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2018).

In recent years, there have been a serious spike in demand for personal development and learning holidays. This situation is changing in line with the new travel trends of tourists for personal development and personal enrichment. Among these new trends, meditation, yoga / pilates, weight loss, detox programs, cooking classes, creative writing can be given as examples. Such self-improvement activities are well suited for solo tourists (CBI Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2018). Many people who plan solo travel are considering adding personal development programs to their travel programs.

4.1.4. Spiritual tourism

Tourism trends are changing and being renewed very rapidly. With the changing and diversifying life styles, it also rapidly differentiates people's expectations from touristic travel. With spiritual travels, tourists want to get away from modern living conditions and bring together cultural discoveries about themselves and the world, and they are in search of the meaning of life. Tourists are able to transfer their endless experience to their worlds by assimilating local culture, belief systems and traditions by establishing a deeper relationship with nature through such travels. Thus, they find calmness, happiness and peace.

In addition to being a journey to a sacred place, temple, belief center that allows one's beliefs, spiritual tourism is a search to find his own essence. In contrast

to the principle of “tourism behavior is temporary and short-lived”, spiritual tourism aims for the tourist to gain experiences that can be valid not only during their travel, but throughout their life. Because at the basis of spiritual tourism are travels that enable the discovery of the inner world and the self rather than acting with religious beliefs. Although spiritual tourism is seen as travel for different purposes such as finding healing in tourism and paying bail, it is a phenomenon that is not known in its scope. However, while it is as old as religious travels, it is one of the oldest travel purposes (Trần, 2013). Visiting religiously holy places such as Mecca, Vatican, Bethlehem (Jerusalem) and India for centuries shows that spiritual purposes were also dominant in ancient times (Rawal & Sah, 2017; Altınay Özdemir et al., 2018, p. 594). Nowadays, with the increase in per capita income, ease of travel and the aging of the population, more and more people participate in overseas travel to be involved in spiritual tourism. Spiritual tourism is recognized as an emerging tourism niche market segment, attracting tourists from all social, cultural and economic segments (Haq, 2015).

The concept of spiritual tourism is based on the philosophy of “the harder the journey, the greater the reward”, which expresses the desire for a comprehensive change rather than the comfort of daily life (Phukan et al., 2012). For this reason, at the basis of spiritual tourism lies the “motive to find the inner self by experiencing the difficult and ordinary life”. This desire to find oneself is possible not only from a religious perspective, but also from a spiritual perspective. Because spiritualism is not always characterized by religion, it is also closely related with the nature or travel to the countryside, recreation, health and culture. Spiritual tourism, which encompasses all these areas, allows tourists to shape their own lives by staying alone with themselves (Trần, 2013).

Spiritual travels are interpreted as “a contemporary and cultural movement”. A psychological quest embedded in the spiritual travel practices of spiritual tourism movements that encourage the use of mind while developing spirituality has brought spirituality tourism movements with it and turned it into a field that can be studied and also applied. The role travel takes in the movement in the pursuit of contemporary spirituality is seen as an interruption to the daily routine pursuit, and also causes spiritual popularity as a reason for the tourism experience. Within the scope of the tourism movement, if spirituality is the main goal, the idea in search or self-discovery will definitely become an accessible travel to experience renewed connections with others or to take advantage of the opportunities offered by life. In this case, spiritual tourism forms touch people, promise to change and improve them (Kandemir Altunel et al., 2020, pp. 156-157).

4.1.5. Yoga tourism

The word *yoga* means “unity” (Aggarwal et al., 2008), and although its roots started in India around 3300 BC (Atkinson, 2010), it is a world-renowned bodily experience whose material and spiritual practices are now known beyond the borders of India (Strauss, 2002). Yoga is a philosophical phenomenon that teaches people to keep their five senses and brain under control. The main goal of yoga is to bring the person to self-awareness. In addition, yoga is regarded as a tool that facilitates a person's intimacy with natural environments and provides transformation into well-being in terms of physical, mental and emotional health (Osho, 2005). Yoga is a path of tranquility that allows people to reconnect to their primary source, due to imperatives, emotional intensity, ego and the complex order created by the human (Mana, 2011).

Yoga, which is the inner path of beliefs based on Indian philosophy, is the ability to give one's thought, emotion and attention to a single point with the state of deep thought, enthusiasm and immersion in spiritual states in order to reach the highest level of knowledge. Yoga, which forms a whole with meanings such as breaking the desires of the soul and training, is the highest level that a person will reach spiritually in order to attain freedom, peace, tranquility and salvation (Şenel, 2018, p. 28).

Yoga tourism is a type of tourism that focuses on the unification of the body, mind and soul, that relaxes and brings peace to people spiritually. The breath and the self are trained in yoga; meditation, physical asanas and breathing techniques are applied to strengthen the body, calm the mind and ultimately provide spiritual enlightenment. Thus, the road to enlightenment is opened and tourists who prefer this route find themselves in yoga tourism (Smith & Kelly, 2006). One of the reasons for the increase in yoga-related travels is the increased interest in activities such as meditation and spa within the scope of health tourism. Another reason is that yoga has begun to be a big step towards spiritual development. Stress, ailments, insomnia, difficulty of city life, fatigue etc. faced by people in modern society life encourage people to participate in yoga tourism due to reasons such as being in touch with nature, desire for an authentic life experience and longing for spiritual peace (Bowers & Cheer, 2017). The person practicing yoga rises as mind and spirit, dominates his body using his brain, and besides physical relaxation, they continue their life by changing their life standards as a philosophy of life (Kandemir Altunel et al., 2020, p. 154).

5. Conclusion

The majority of the population around the world consists of people born between 1980 and 1996. Today, the young and new adult generation isn't at all like the previous X generation, who took their families as role models. It is a generation that doesn't like monotony at all. Millennials, who use technology effectively and actively, has a tendency to adopt by obtaining information about fashion and trends quickly. When the tourist behavior of this generation in making travel decision is examined, features such as entertainment seeking, price tracking, motivational action, perfectionist-seeking high quality, pursuit of innovation, adherence to preferences draw attention. In addition, 9 out of every 10 millennial tourists are definitely in search of a new experience during their travels and research about the destination they will go from various information sources before going out on the trip. In terms of travel preferences, “personalized experience”, “digital comfort” and “social media” are indispensable for the millennials who seek adventure and discovery.

While planning their travels, they make reservations online and use social media more actively. They consult their friends and circles to read the comments of travel and accommodation businesses on social platforms, to evaluate their experiences and recommendations, and to make purchasing decisions. In this context, it is very important for tourism businesses to keep up with the times, to follow technological developments and to use social media effectively for customer satisfaction and customer continuity.

Millennials, who will determine the shape of the tourism sector in the near future, demand to discover new experiences such as excursions full of activities, authentic experiences, spiritual relaxations and purification, freedom instead of the general tourism trends, which are the relaxation and rest-oriented tourism approach shaped in the sea, sand, sun triangle. Although the older generations still have a tendency to relax and rest, millennials prefer tourism types that are focused on personal experience, called “experience tourism”. Millennials, who tend to experience the life of the local people living in their destination and explore more virgin areas, adopt more freedom to travel with less goods. Many destinations from around the world are allocating resources to develop tourism segments for millennials. At this point, tourism enterprises should direct their activities by taking into account the expectations and travel behaviors of this generation.

Broad transformations in people's quest to do different things in their lives have started to change the travel pattern and gradually direct it to the destinations where spiritual, physical and mental activities are performed. In addition, the

principle of “finding one's own essence” comes to the fore in the travels of this generation. Going deep into their own culture, understanding their ancestors and finding their own essence are also an important travel goal for this generation. In addition, people can communicate with local people and have authentic experience, taking into account the principles of sustainable development and they are among the current tourism trends.

With the changing social order, people's lifestyles have begun to change. Especially in Europe, more and more people live alone, pushing people to search for new freedom. Solo tourism activities are included in the travel preferences of people who live alone or live in a crowded family and want to travel alone, who want to move freely in their travels. Camp tourism, which is carried out by those who want to be alone with nature, preferred by solo travel, responds to the understanding of socially distant vocation in recent years, especially due to the pandemic in 2020. The last trend of 2020 has been accepted as the tourism activity. As a result, people's desire to stay alone with themselves in nature, the desire to go on an internal journey, mental renewal, camp tourism, spiritual tourism, wellness tourism, yoga tourism and solo tourism, which are among the types of tourism that give the opportunity to feel better, are tourism activities with increasing demand in recent years. It would be beneficial for travel agencies to follow the tourist behavior and travel preferences of this segment and to act according to the current demands in order to respond to the waits of this generation.

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